

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF USING SOFTWARE IN PARAMETRIC MODELING OF POWER MACHINES

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Abstract

This article aims to review software tools for parametric modeling of electromechanical energy converters. These tools significantly improve the quality of calculations and design of structural components of power machines and units. The paper analyzes existing software tools for modeling various types of electrical machines and substantiates the feasibility of using known CAD programs exclusively for solving applied engineering problems. However, to obtain results in experimental design or the design of electrical machines for which there are no analogues (in terms of design or operational characteristics), it is necessary to develop additional software or write a separate program. Three software packages are distinguished among those improving parametric design: SolidWorks, T-FLEX CAD, and COMSOL Multiphysics. It has been established that, from a functional standpoint, the development of such a software block is practical for multiparametric design, where efficiency is achieved through the simultaneous modeling of the electrodynamic, gasdynamic, mechanical, and thermal processes of the electrical machine.

Keywords: Power machines, parametric modeling, electrodynamic, mechanical and thermal processes, energy conversion.

Relevance of the research problem

Currently, automated design systems are useful for designing energy machines based on the conversion of various types of energy within the confines of parametric design. Such methodological tools significantly improve the quality of design and scientific work. However, the use of software for modeling electrodynamic, gasdynamic, thermal, and mechanical processes requires a methodical description of their implementation features and conditions [1]. In this paper, we will review modern software for modeling electromechanical energy converters.

The aim of the article is to analyze existing automated design systems for power machines within the framework of the implementation of a parametric methodology for the development and creation of modern, competitive electrical machines.

Material and essence of the research

As software tools for parametric modeling of an electromechanical energy converter, we will define the following software packages as those that have commanded their effectiveness and efficiency, namely: SolidWorks, T-FLEX CAD and COMSOL Multiphysics.

1. The SolidWorks program is a CAD software package for automating the work of an industrial enterprise at the stages of design and technological preparation of production. It provides the development of products of any degree of complexity and purpose. The SolidWorks software package includes various application modules [2, 3]:

- engineering data management: SolidWorks Enterprise PDM;
- engineering calculations: SolidWorks Simulation, and SolidWorks Flow Simulation;
- electrical design: SolidWorks Electrical;

- development of interactive documentation: SolidWorks Composer;
- machining, CNC machining: CAMWorks;
- data verification: CAMWorks Virtual Machine;
- quality control: SolidWorks Inspection;
- manufacturability analysis: SolidWorks Plastics, DFM.

For the design of electromechanical structures, their calculation and further analysis, we will be interested in the following three modules of the program: SolidWorks Electrical, SolidWorks Simulation, and SolidWorks Flow Simulation. Let's consider their features.

The composition of the electrical design module includes:

a) SolidWorks Electrical Schematic is a multifunctional 2D system for designing electrical circuits. Design of logical, structural, electrical circuits, block diagrams of cable connections, connection tables, etc., using the nomenclature database of components from global manufacturers of radio electronics. Automatic numbering and labeling of project components with real-time update. Two-dimensional layout of components in cabinets and modules. Creation of documentation and reports based on project data. Joint work of developers on a digital layout of the electrical component of the product taking into account changes in real time. Ability to use developments in DWG/DXF format;

b) SolidWorks Electrical 3D is a 3D layout of electrical cabinets based on 2D project data and a large database of 3D models of components. Automatic wiring, taking into account cable channels. Automatic division of cable system routing into power and signal lines. Calculation of cable channel occupancy.

SolidWorks Simulation – is responsible for calculations of the strength of structures in the elastic zone,

formulation and solution of contact problems, calculation of assemblies; determination of natural forms and frequencies of oscillations, calculation of the structure for stability, fatigue calculations, fall simulation, thermal calculations. Optimization of SolidWorks Motion model parameters: comprehensive dynamic and kinematic analysis of mechanisms, determination of speeds, accelerations and mutual influences of system elements. In addition, it allows you to perform nonlinear calculations: accounting for nonlinear material properties, nonlinear loading, calculation of nonlinear contact problems; analysis of long-term loading and determination of the resource of structures. Linear and nonlinear dynamics of deformable systems. Optimization of model parameters taking into account the mechanical nature of the load. Calculation of multilayer composite shells and much more.

SolidWorks Flow Simulation is a module designed to perform simulation of the flow of liquids and gases, control of the computational grid, use of typical physical models of liquids and gases, complex thermal calculation, gas and hydrodynamic and thermal models of technical devices, non-dynamic and non-stationary analysis, calculation of rotating objects, export of results to SolidWorks Simulation. In addition, the Electronic Cooling Add-In performs thermal calculations of

electronic devices. It has an expanded database of virtual fans; electrical materials, thermoelectric coolers (Peltier elements), two-resistor components. Simulation of the passage of direct current and heating by direct current, models of two-resistor components, heat pipes and channels.

Of course, the SolidWorks software package is a powerful tool for high-quality development, modeling and forecasting the state of machines and mechanisms, but in the context of designing electrical machines it is useful only in solving problems of a thermal, ventilation (hydraulic) and mechanical nature. The program perfectly solves the problems of complex mechanical loading in combination with thermal loads on parts and assemblies of an electrical machine. It also qualitatively solves the problems of studying the state of an electrical machine that has already worked out its standard service life, or in the mode of long-term operation under load.

Preliminary results of modeling the magnetic field in the core of a simple transformer, performed in the SolidWorks program, are presented in Fig. 1. According to the received report, the tendency of the magnetic field inhomogeneity and the concentration of increased load in the corners of the magnetic core is clearly visible.

Figure 1. Results of modeling the magnetic field in the core of a simple transformer, performed in SolidWorks

The main advantages of using the SolidWorks program are as follows:

- clear, classic program interface, as for any solid-state design program of the CAD family;
- logical construction of both geometric and mathematical models is implemented, according to the "step-by-step" principle;
- a sufficiently large library of template geometric models, a large library of materials (metals and non-metals), well-developed interaction when working with national and industry standards (DSTU, ISO, DIN, ASME);
- sufficiently high-quality implementation of modeling of mechanical, thermal and ventilation processes in combination with relatively low requirements for computer resource power (depends on the number of parts in the assembly and the detail of the calculation grid);

- allows several designers to work on the development simultaneously;
- there are enough sources of information in free access to answer questions of a narrow specialty, or to solve "single-case" problems.

The main disadvantages of the program include:

- there is not enough functionality for deeper work with the electromagnetic component of modeling, modeling of the mechanical and thermal state of the machine is implemented much better;
- when building a geometric model, it requires a more detailed definition of the initial data, with an insufficient amount of initial data (unfortunately, this is sometimes dictated by reality) the modeling results will be incorrect and unsuitable for further use;
- to obtain high-quality development results, the developer's qualification level is higher than average.

2. T-FLEX CAD is an engineering computer-aided design system that combines parametric capabilities of 2D and 3D modeling with tools for creating and designing drawings and design documentation in accordance with the ESKD and foreign standards (ISO, DIN, ANSI). The scope of application is general mechanical engineering, including the construction of power machines and mechanisms and aircraft. The main functionality of the program is the following [4, 5]:

- parametric 2D sketching and parametric 2D/3D design using hybrid parameterization, which combines classical parameterization based on construction elements and dimensional parameterization based on constraints and control dimensions;
- direct reading and import of formats of various CAD systems; export to formats of other CAD systems;
- full associative relationship between the 3D model and its drawing;
- a set of tools for preparing design documentation in accordance with the ESKD, ISO, DIN and ANS standards;
- the ability to combine the methods of work "bottom-up" (from part to assembly) and "top-down" (from assembly to part);
- work with reference geometry with the ability to manage the update process;

- there are tools for collective work with projects;
- engineering express analysis of parts by means of finite elements;
- API interface for developing your own programs;
- variable editor using multi-line expressions and syntax highlighting;
- support for working with internal and external databases;
- libraries of parametric 2D and 3D standard elements.

As in the above-mentioned software complexes and individual modules, in

T-FLEX CAD, the modeling process of various types of tasks and engineering studies using MSE tools is implemented at a high level. T-FLEX CAD is a relatively young development tool, but quite effective for solving problems of the mechanical and thermal state of an electric machine. The calculation component of aerodynamic processes is excellently performed, and allows you to calculate all possible flow losses, which, for example, are necessary to remove excess heat from the slot channel of the stator winding. The parameterization of the models is performed according to the hybrid type (geometric, tabular). Fig. 2 shows a part of the electromechanical energy converter, made in the T-FLEX CAD program.

Figure 2. Part of an electromechanical energy converter (reducer) made in the T-FLEX CAD program

The main advantages of using the T-FLEX CAD program are as follows:

- an intuitive set of tools for designing and building a geometric structure;
- the mathematical apparatus of calculations is based on the foundations of the MFE, and is not limited to it;
- the program provides wide opportunities for developing drawings, which significantly speeds up the design work on the project

The main disadvantages of the program include:

- insufficient functionality for better work on modeling and research of the electromagnetic compo-

nent of the unit, modeling of the mechanical and thermal state of the machine is implemented somewhat better;

- the program requires constant monitoring and analysis of intermediate results of the calculation stages from the developer.

3. COMSOL Multiphysics is a general-purpose modeling software used in all areas of design, manufacturing, and research. This software suite provides fully integrated multiphysics and single-physics modeling capabilities, model management, and easy-to-use tools for creating simulation programs. Additional software modules provide specialized functionality in the fields of electromagnetics, structural mechanics, acoustics,

fluid flow, heat transfer, and chemical engineering. All additional products in the product suite easily connect to COMSOL Multiphysics for a modeling workflow that remains the same no matter what you are modeling.

The functionality of the program is very extensive, covering almost all areas of design, and is described in more detail in [6, 7]. COMSOL Multiphysics performs its work using the following program components:

- Electromagnetics module;
- Structural mechanics and acoustics module;
- Fluid flow and heat transfer module;
- Chemical engineering module;
- Multipurpose products module;
- Interface products module.

To implement the design and optimization of electrical machines, an electromagnetic module is used. To develop and evaluate the mechanical and thermal state of an electrical machine, a structural mechanics and acoustics module, and a fluid flow and heat transfer module are used. The mathematical apparatus used to perform calculations is MSE. Parameterization is implemented in a hybrid type.

The available functionality of the electromagnetic module for rotating machines simplifies the modeling

of motors and generators. For example, you can study the behavior of induction or permanent magnet motors, in particular, by recording the eddy current losses that arise inside the magnets. In any model used to model electromagnetic motion, you can study the dynamics of a rigid or flexible body under the influence of magnetic forces and moments, induced currents, as well as mechanical loads and configurations of the structural parts of an electrical machine. A universal moving grid allows you to model linear motion. This is important for understanding the operation of components that include plungers, such as magnetic power switches, solenoids, and general drives. Modeling losses in laminated iron cores and yokes of electric motors and transformers is necessary to predict their efficiency and performance. In particular, for laminated iron (electrical steel), empirical models of electromagnetic losses are important because macroscale Joule heating or induction heating cannot fully describe the effect that causes losses. At the same time, modeling laminates separately is often impractical. Fig. 3 shows a geometric model for studying losses in an electric motor.

Figure 3. Geometric model for studying losses in an electric motor, made in the COMSOL Multiphysics program

The main advantages of using the COMSOL Multiphysics program are:

- results of modeling a wide range of multiphysical phenomena and processes are obtained, combined with a high degree of adequacy and accuracy of calculations;
- accurate multiphysical models take into account a wide range of operating conditions and a large set of materials and templates, which qualitatively increases the speed and efficiency of using the program;
- in comparison with the research functionality, COMSOL Multiphysics shows the best result among all CAD system programs;
- a set of tools for designing and building a research model is accessible to mastering;
- the main disadvantages of the program include:

- it is extremely important for the developer to have confident programming skills;
- requires powerful computer equipment and accompanying modern software;
- to obtain high-quality development results, the developer's qualification level is above average.

Conclusion

As a result of the analysis of existing software tools for modeling electromechanical energy converters, it has been proven that the use of well-known CAD programs is advisable only for solving applied engineering problems, but to obtain results in experimental design or design of power machines for which there are no analogues (in terms of design or operating conditions), it is necessary to develop an additional software

block or write an individual program. It has been established that writing such a software block is advisable, from a functional point of view, to be performed within the framework of multiparametric design, where efficiency is achieved due to the simultaneous modeling of electromagnetic, electromechanical and heat-ventilation processes of a power machine.

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